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Introduction

4 Since September 11, 2001, over 2.5 million US Service Members were stationed in Africa
5 and the Middle East¹. Advancements in modern medicine are improving survivability from severe
6 combat induced injuries¹⁻⁴. The wounded to fatality rate increased from 5.2 to 1 during the Vietnam
7 War to 7.6 to 1 during Operation Iraqi Freedom (OIF), and the annual number of people killed in
8 a combat zone decreased from 2,231 per 100,000 to 416 per 100,000⁴. While the Middle East to
9 Vietnam casualty ratio shows improved survivability, approximately 32,000 Service Members
10 were medically airlifted out of a combat zone in Iraq because of an injury, equivalent to 4,400 for
11 every 100,000 Service Members per year^{4,5}. Several combat trauma survivors live with a chronic
12 disability that affects their ability to ambulate and participate as independent members of society⁶⁻
13 ¹⁰. Between 3% and 9% of all wounded in action received a major limb amputation, 11% sustained
14 spine related trauma, and up to 23% of deployed Service Members sustained a traumatic brain
15 injury (TBI) as a result of combat operations¹⁰.

16 Long-term medical complications impact the rehabilitation from traumatic injury¹¹. People
17 with Spinal Cord Injury (SCI) are 2.72 times more likely to contract some form of cardiovascular
18 disease compared to those without an SCI¹². Survivors of limb loss injuries are likely to experience
19 gait misalignment, which may result in postural difficulties and increased metabolic expenditure
20 during walking/running activities¹³. People with TBI also potentially experience difficulties with
21 ambulation¹⁴. Trauma is also associated with an increased risk for posttraumatic stress disorder
22 (PTSD)¹⁵. Approximately 20% of people with an SCI report at least partial symptoms for PTSD,
23 while TBI tends to overlap a PTSD diagnosis because of similarities in mood and emotional
24 instability^{16,17}. Trauma and PTSD can also lead to sleep deprivation, depression, substance abuse,
25 and suicidal ideation¹⁶⁻²⁰.

1 Mobility related Assistive Technology, referring to medical equipment that assists with
2 ambulation and mobility, is used by approximately 3.6 million Americans^{21, 22}. Examples of this
3 technology include, but are not limited to, wheelchairs, prosthetics, orthotics, exoskeletons,
4 smartphone apps for mobility, and internet of things^{21, 22}. Applications of mobility related Assistive
5 Technologies improves a Veteran’s ability to live independently while adapting to life with a
6 disability^{21, 22}. For instance, a prosthetic offers advanced swing control which provides improved
7 symmetry and gait velocity in potentially active survivors of limb loss¹³. Rehabilitation services
8 that support and train individuals on wheelchair use improves self-efficacy and one’s ability to live
9 independently^{23, 24}. Smartphone-based interventions, such as those involving applications that
10 reframed self-perception to identify one’s strengths and abilities, have also been shown to be
11 effective among people with disabilities, including TBI²⁴.

12 Developing the capability to adapt to a traumatic injury and Assistive Technology is
13 instrumental to the level of one’s health related quality of life (HR-QoL)²⁵⁻²⁷. According to the
14 World Health Organization (WHO), HR-QoL is defined as “an individual’s perception of their
15 position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to
16 their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns.”²⁶. HR-QoL, overall, is frequently assessed with
17 scales such as the EQ-5D, SF-36, WHO-15, and others. However, measuring specific aspects of
18 quality of life is challenging, because perceptions of HR-QoL may differ based on culture,
19 environment, and personal preferences. Therefore, HR-QoL measurement is frequently assessed
20 from multiple health outcomes to address physical, mental, and social health domains and
21 subdomains²⁶.

22 To date, there is a paucity of literature on the health outcomes used to measure and model
23 HR-QoL domains and subdomains when recovering from, and adapting to, a mobility based

1 assistive technology induced by combat injury. The goal of this research was to use the WHO
2 HR-QoL domains as reference and identify, and categorize, health outcome measures that are
3 used track facets of HR-QoL in post 9/11 Veterans rehabilitating a combat injury with mobility
4 based Assistive Technology. There were four aims in this review: (1) investigate health
5 outcomes literature reported on post 9/11 Veterans living with a combat induced mobility
6 impairment, (2) determine the state of the science on this literature, (3) categorize the study's
7 health outcomes into the appropriate HR-QoL domains and subdomains, and (4) summarize how
8 these outcome measures are useful to track and measure the HR-QoL for this unique health state.
9 Information collected from this review is useful when researching specific HR-QoL states and
10 identifying how to best model the recovery process and effectiveness of an intervention.

11

12 **Methods**

13 *Review Process*

14 The scoping literature review was conducted with assistance from a librarian at the
15 University of Pittsburgh Health Science Library. Subject headings and keywords were selected to
16 identify research reports relevant to the major components of the review: post 9/11 conflicts,
17 military services, lower extremity injury or disability, and health related quality of life outcomes.
18 The full Medline (PubMed) search strategy is included in Appendix A.

19 The librarian searched the Medline (PubMed), CINHAHL (Ebsco), EMBASE
20 (Embase.com), and PsycINFO (Ovid) databases on June 27, 2019 from 2001 – 2019. Studies
21 included met the follow criteria: (1) original research studies that included health outcomes
22 relevant to a combat induced mobility impairment; (2) focused on a human population; (3)
23 population was over 18 years old; (4) included national and international Veterans or Active Duty

1 personnel; (5) study participants partook in worldwide conflicts occurring after 9/11; (6) addressed
2 a health outcome that fit into a domain described in the WHO HR-QoL. Studies were excluded for
3 the following reasons: (1) participants were injured in civilian incidents (i.e. highway accidents,
4 etc.); (2) the study did not state whether their cohort included people with a mobility impairment;
5 (3) only included Veterans from pre-9/11 conflicts; (4) were not published in English nor had a
6 full article form available.

7 Studies extracted from the literature review were compiled and uploaded to the Distiller
8 (DistillerSR) software for screening and extraction. Three investigators, all with backgrounds in
9 rehabilitation science, were involved with screening: (1) a bioengineer, (2) a human movement
10 scientist, and (3) an epidemiologist. Abstracts were included for an additional full-article screening
11 if they met the inclusion criteria. Abstracts with an element of uncertainty regarding the eligibility
12 criteria were also included in the article screening. Final study inclusion was determined based on
13 an investigator agreement on the screening criteria. Articles that qualified after the full article
14 screening were included in the review and key information was extracted from these reports.

15

16 *Data Extraction*

17 In the data extraction process, investigators took note of the study authors, the demographic
18 characteristics of the study populations, the primary injury or injuries assessed, injury mechanisms,
19 the types of assistive technology mentioned in the study, and time since the injury and the study
20 period. Additionally, investigators recorded the type of study design used in each report. The
21 degree of selection and information bias relevant to each study was determined based off evidence
22 strength in the research hierarchy, personal experience with research methodology, and through a
23 three point number scale; “1” indicated the study carried High selection or information biases, a

1 “2” indicated Moderate biases, while a “3” indicated Low to no biases. Key components to
2 examine the level of biases were based upon research factors that minimize bias, such as sample
3 size, blinding, data collection, inclusion of a control group, and randomization. For instance,
4 randomized controlled trials would score a “3,” or “Low,” for both selection and information
5 biases. Case studies or single subject designs would score “1,” or “High,” for both selection and
6 information biases.

7 Extracted health outcome measures were stratified into tables based on WHO established
8 HR-QoL domains and sub-domains (Figure 1) and investigator-rated relevance to in the
9 rehabilitation sciences. Criteria and definitions used to classify health outcomes by domain and
10 subdomain are found in the Supplemental Table 1²⁶.

11

12 **Results**

13 A total of 3682 results were retrieved from PubMed, Embase, CINAHL, and PsycINFO.
14 After duplicate records were removed, 2408 records were eligible for screening. Following the
15 initial abstract screening, 609 articles remained for full article review which yielded 224 articles
16 based off inclusion and exclusion criteria.

17 Subsequently, these 224 articles were screened for mention of the application of assistive
18 technology (i.e. mobility aids). The final included a total of 38 articles²⁸⁻⁶⁵. The process can be
19 seen in Supplemental Table 2 and full results are observed in Supplemental Tables 3-9.

20

21 *Demographic Information and the State of the Science Demographics*

22

23 Of the 38 articles examined, 4488 participants were included in this review with the largest
24 study containing 964 participants and the smallest study containing one person. Of the studies that
25 tracked gender (N=23), 1769 (79%) of the total participants were male. Age of study participants

1 was between 25-31 years old in 18 (47%) studies. The average age was approximately 28 years
2 old. The United States was the study nationality in 29 (76%) articles, with additional research from
3 the United Kingdom (N=4 (10%)), the Netherlands (N=2 (5%)), Denmark (N=1 (3%)), Pakistan
4 (N=1 (3%)), and Iran (N=1 (3%)). There was variation in the time from injury in the studies.
5 Approximately 31% or 12 articles included participants injured between “1 to 5 years” prior but
6 14 (37%) studies were “Undefined.” Graphs of full results can be seen in Figure 1 below and in
7 Supplemental Table 3.

8

9 *Injury, Mechanisms, and Assistive Technology*

10 Of the injuries assessed in each of the studies, 26 (68%) of reports included participants
11 with amputations and/or limb salvage. Explosion (i.e. blast or high impact injuries) was the
12 primary injury mechanism in 17 (45%) studies, but 18 (47%) studies focused on general combat
13 injuries or were undefined. Of the primary mobility based Assistive Technology addressed,
14 prosthetics and/or orthotics were reported in 25 (66%) articles. Of the “Other” Assistive
15 Technology category, one (3%) focused on “Smartphone Applications” and one (3%) included
16 “Prescription Shoes.” The full results can be seen in Figure 2 below and Supplemental Table 3.

17

18 *Study Design Strength and Biases*

19 The studies collected for the review were predominately observational studies (N=20
20 (53%)), with 12 (32%) retrospective cohorts. Figure 3 also illustrates the results of the assessment
21 of the degree of selection and information bias rated in these reports. Nineteen (53%) of the studies
22 were rated as having high selection bias while 17 (45%) of the studies were rated as having

1 moderate levels of information bias. The full results can be seen in Figure 3 below and
 2 Supplemental Table 3.

3

4 *Health Related Quality of Life Outcomes*

5 Of the articles with health outcomes that qualified for physical health (N=17 (45%)), five
 6 (13%) fell into the “Energy and Fatigue” subdomain and 12 (32%) fell under “Pain and
 7 Discomfort”²⁸⁻⁴⁴. Of the articles in the psychological well-being domain (N=11 (29%)), two (5%)
 8 articles qualified for the cognition subdomain, eight (21%) were placed under “Negative
 9 Emotions,” two (5%) in “Positive Domains,” and one (3%) for “Self-Esteem”^{29,33,34,37,41,42,45-48,65}.
 10 Of the “Independence” papers (N=21 (55%)), 17 ((45%) fit into the “Mobility” subdomain while
 11 four (10%) focused on “Activities of Daily Living”^{24,30,31,34,35,39,42-44,46,49-58}. Of the Social Relations
 12 studies (N=6 (16%)), four focused on the “Social Support” subdomain while two (5%) focused on
 13 “Personal Relationships”^{33,34,41,59,60}. Of the “Environment” domain (N=11 (29%)), nine (24%)
 14 studies focused on “Health and Social Care: Accessibility and Quality” while two (5%) were
 15 grouped into “Participation in and Opportunities for Recreation/Leisure”^{34,39,43,48,53,59,61-63}. Three
 16 (8%) studies were grouped into “Religious/Spiritual/Personal Beliefs” domain^{59, 61,64}.
 17 Supplemental Tables 4-9 details specific outcomes used.

18

19 **Discussion**

20 The purpose of this study was to review the literature and categorize the key health
 21 outcomes examined for Service Members rehabilitating from, and adapting to life with, a combat
 22 injury. This expanded on overall HR-QoL measurement tools to include individual, as opposed to
 23 just collective, facets of HR-QoL. Doing so provides future researchers, clinicians, and decision

1 makers a tool to find out how to best model different aspects of a client’s health state during the
2 recovery process.

3 Approximately 50% of the articles reviewed were observational studies that assessed
4 Service Members adapting to a prosthetic after a blast-related amputation. Instruments used to
5 measure one’s physical and psychological states, independence and social relations, and
6 environmental navigation and personal beliefs were able to provide an observation on how
7 different facets of HR-QoL are measured during rehabilitation and the impact of an intervention,
8 in this case mobility related Assistive Technology. As expected, there is a paucity of literature
9 based on contemporary nature of the topic. For instance, there was a lack of studies with wheelchair
10 users, exoskeletons, and smartphone-based TBI interventions. A summary of the key findings in
11 this review follows.

12

13 *Physical Health Outcomes*

14 The studies in the Physical Health domain identified health outcomes that assessed Pain
15 and Discomfort in post 9/11 combat Veterans. This indicated to us that combat induced mobility
16 impairment and Assistive Technology studies focused on the impacts of participant injuries,
17 comorbid physical conditions that accompanied the primary injury, and the severity of discomfort
18 during an intervention.

19 Pain and Discomfort based measures included those assessing the frequency and intensity
20 of arthritis, chronic back pain, residual limb pain, and migraines^{30,33,34}. This is because of
21 complications, such as sores and ossification, that occur during surgery and difficulties with
22 walking shortly after an injury, as seen in studies taking place less than 5 years since injury^{29,34,38}.
23 Additionally, information on infection was frequently collected among those papers featuring a

1 late amputation sample³⁸. This indicated that deterioration of the wound is affected by the
2 prolonged time frame between initial injury and amputation, creating discomfort and additional
3 health problems³⁸. Phantom limb pain, a phenomenon caused by changes in the peripheral and
4 central nervous system following amputation, was commonly asked about in studies reporting
5 research on amputees⁴³. This comorbidity is a source of discomfort among this population and
6 should be observed during one's rehabilitation⁴³. A similar report using the RAND-36 DLV found
7 poor physical HR-QoL in 437 amputees complaining of phantom limb pain, citing stump pain an
8 important factor when determining status of HR-QoL⁶⁶.

9 Data on adaption to a mobility related Assistive Technology was also collected to assess
10 instances of pain and discomfort, in addition to energy expenditure^{29,32,34,35,42,43,57}. This included
11 observations on physical functioning change that occur as amputees became more comfortable
12 with their assistive technology throughout the duration of rehabilitation³³. Outcomes for energy
13 expenditure utilized ankle biomechanics metabolic functioning, and spatiotemporal outcomes,
14 which investigators collected and compared with non-injured controls^{28,32,35}.

15

16 *Psychological Health*

17 Outcomes measures categorized in this domain focused primarily on the Negative
18 Emotions the population experienced while recovering from a combat injury. This finding
19 exemplifies the necessity to measure the short- and long-term influence of a stressful experience
20 on one's psychological HR-QoL, particularly when recovering from an injury.

21 Investigators recorded data with PTSD, depression, and anxiety based instruments, such as
22 the posttraumatic stress disorder checklist (PCL-5) and personal health questionnaire (PHQ), in
23 approximately half of amputee and limb salvage military populations^{41,47,65}. According to the Fifth

1 Edition of the Diagnostics and Statistics Manual for Mental Disorders, traumatic events heighten
2 a survivor's sensitivity, which is potentially exacerbated when rehabilitating an injury⁶⁷. Between
3 the increasing survival rate and changing social landscape towards addressing mental health,
4 particularly in the military, PTSD is addressed with the same urgency and care as one's amputation
5 would be^{1,43}. To reduce negative impacts of a disability, it is imperative to track these conditions
6 when adhering to an intervention^{41, 47, 65}. Investigators collected information on cognition with
7 psychometric surveys and clinical assessments outlined in Kontos et al 2015⁴⁸. Cognitive
8 impairments resulting from a TBI impact emotional and physical states due to injury mechanism
9 and time between injury and intervention application⁴³. Therefore, if a participant reports a TBI
10 diagnosis, it is imperative to ensure it is addressed during recovery. The outcomes of our review
11 confirmed similar psychological well-being-based HR-QoL outcomes in a study of 2469 adults
12 who reported a correlation between poor mental health and an amputation compared to those with
13 a less serious injury that did not require assistance⁶⁸.

14 Outcomes assessing Assistive Technology use found additional inquiry into the emotional
15 impact of mobility based Assistive Technology on the recovery process, as seen in a study of
16 Amputees at a Prosthetic Training Center in the UK^{33,37}. Assistive Technology usability was also
17 measured when addressing cognitive symptoms related to a combat induced TBI³⁷. Vestibular
18 oculomotor movement instrumentation was used to measure impacts of a mobile health
19 intervention on balance and coordination³⁷. As the world continues to use such technology,
20 evidence based mobile health interventions, such as ecological momentary assessments, mindful
21 breathing, and symptom trackers, may find increased application injury rehabilitation because of
22 their accessibility, privacy, and the lack of a financial burden³⁷. When applying these interventions

1 to a client with a TBI, vestibular oculomotor movement tests offer a methodology to judge the
2 progress a client is making during their recovery³⁷.

3

4 *Independence*

5 For the Independence domain, the review found that most study outcomes fit into the
6 Mobility subdomain, confirming focus on mobility related issues facing Veterans recovering from
7 a combat induced injury. A previous report using the SF-36 identified this as a predominant issue
8 when discussing HR-QoL with a similar population⁶⁷.

9 These measurement tools were used to track ambulation following an injury. Health
10 outcomes in this subdomain recorded potential differences with walking for longer periods of time
11 and running one block amongst post combat Amputees^{31,42-44}. Differing levels of mobility
12 function, using a self-reported survey, were reported for various activities and tasks in participants
13 in Eskridge et al 2019⁵⁵. This is useful for research and feedback on the ability to complete mobility
14 tasks independently, such as getting in and out of chair or walking multiple hours a day^{39,46,55}.

15 Health outcomes observing Independence are crucial to track adaptation to a mobility
16 based Assistive Technology. For instance, investigators researching independence used
17 spatiotemporal data, collected during initial prosthetic fitting, and kinematics to determine
18 differences in knee flexion in stance phase and average plantarflexion and dorsiflexion on initial
19 contact with the ground^{30,39,44}. After initial prosthetic fitting, it was critical that Veterans, and their
20 clinicians, keep track of walking parameters, in order to adjust an intervention as best seen fit^{35,48,49}.
21 Researchers also used spatiotemporal outcome to determine exoskeleton performance on various
22 validated assessments as well as when investigating on novel orthotics, indicating a need to
23 continue inquiring into novel technological interventions to improve mobility and

1 independence^{35,51,53}. Additionally, researchers asked Veterans about usability of a Walker or Cane
2 in order to ensure they easily moved from place to place on their own⁴³. Self-reported feedback
3 detailed the perceptions of a client as they are rehabilitating their injury⁴³. Additionally, we noted
4 that rehabilitation progress, age, and comfort with Assistive Technology is responsible for
5 independence levels among Veteran populations⁵⁵. Data collected on these factors was useful when
6 comparing older and younger cohorts and is critical to address in future research⁵⁵.

7

8 *Social Relations*

9 Health outcomes reported in Social Relations studies were predominately categorized in
10 the Social Support subdomain. This showed the impact of social support on one's ability to recover
11 and rehabilitate a combat induced mobility impairment. These aligned with measures used in a
12 prior SF-36 based study which concluded that increased social support was a necessity for better
13 HR-QoL in amputees⁶⁹.

14 The literature stresses the importance of tracking a social support network of friends and
15 family, in addition to the strength of that network, because of the comfort it provides during
16 adaptation to a disability⁵⁹. For instance, a Veteran, using a power wheelchair for an SCI, was
17 asked to describe personal feelings about his family's empathy towards his emotional states, injury,
18 and rehab their impact on his well-being⁵⁹. Such outcome measures are coupled with research
19 reporting the opposite outcomes; how lack of social network during recovery leads to poor HR-
20 QoL^{59,60}. However social functioning and role limitations measurement tools differed amongst
21 those rehabilitating different types of amputations and requires further investigation^{33,34}.

22 Outcomes reporting a secure social support network were also crucial in determining
23 progress adapting to Assistive Technology. Role functioning, both physical and emotional,

1 changes over the course of the recovery process from first measurement to the last measurement
2 period³³. This is due to adjustments in confidence when adapting to the technology while also
3 coming to terms with a disability¹¹. For instance, the individual in the power wheelchair was asked
4 about motivation from his family when adapting to his wheelchair, which assists social functioning
5 and the ability to confidently participate with others in society^{11,34,59}.

6

7 *Environment*

8 Health outcomes in this review were placed predominately in the Accessibility to, and
9 Quality of, Health and Social Care subdomain. This indicated that accessibility and quality of
10 disability related services is a primary factor for determining the HR-QoL in injured combat
11 Veterans.

12 It is critical for Veterans with mobility impairments to be engaged in services and activities
13 that build confidence and provide a safe-haven to continue socialization and integration^{11,39}. One
14 distinct example found in the review was measurements on access to well organized exercise and
15 recreational events, a crucial activity of daily living amongst Veterans with mobility
16 impairments³⁹. Participation in adaptive sports was measured while attending a popular annual
17 event funded by the Department of Veterans Affairs³⁹. This represents the need to assess
18 participation in society as a crucial outcome when determining facets of one's HR-QoL³⁹.
19 Furthermore, it compliments with prior literature that also addressed the benefit of access to
20 adaptive sports, based on participation time playing adaptive basketball⁷⁰.

21 With regards to Assistive Technology, outcome measures collected in the review indicated
22 Veterans are equally involved in the design and development of technologies that adhere to their
23 more active, comfortable lifestyle^{39,43,59,62}. For instance, one study compared usability of

1 prosthetics and wheelchairs required by OIF/OEF and Vietnam War Veterans using a self-reported
2 survey⁴³. Such data would assist with differences that result from years since injury and its impact
3 on Assistive Technology based necessities (i.e. designs to a basketball wheelchair)^{39,43,70}.
4 Additionally, the review investigators categorized outcome measures that determined gender based
5 usability into this category⁶². Improperly fitted, poor quality prosthetics increase risk for falling
6 and diminished participation in activities outside the home while prosthetics were likely to fail at
7 least once⁴³. This is problematic if the design of the technology is intrinsically biased towards one
8 gender⁴³. Therefore, quality of gender-based services should be included as a measurement tool in
9 the future. Furthermore, Veterans with an SCI and a wheelchair were asked about personal
10 environments and the assistance provided by caregivers when adapting to life with their injury⁵⁹.
11 Advancing quality and accessibility to appropriate services are crucial for rehabilitation and one's
12 ability to participate in independent members of society.

13

14 *Religious/Spiritual/Personal Beliefs*

15 A combat injury, and the rehabilitation that followed, influenced religious, spiritual, and
16 personal beliefs amongst Service Members. Wounded Warriors, athletes, and people with SCI
17 were asked about their attitudes towards different groups which was used to expose potential pre-
18 existing stigmas facing these populations⁶¹.

19 Veterans using wheelchairs and prosthetics after a combat injury reported on adherence to
20 the military lifestyle, positivity level, and faith⁶⁴. Patients with SCI and using wheelchairs also
21 reported on trust, which was also collected from female prosthetic users and is used to determine
22 the strength and beliefs of community support networks⁵⁹. These outcomes stress the importance

1 of tracking personal feelings and abilities towards themselves, and members of their community,
2 in order to ensure they are less

3

4 *Limitations and Future Research*

5 Few experimental designs were utilized from studies collected in this review. This is
6 understandable, because of the novel nature of the population of interest. However, evidence-based
7 guidelines generally require evidence from experimental trials. Future research studies in this topic
8 area should incorporate randomized controlled trial designs assessing the outcome of different
9 interventions in addition to further comparison to healthy controls. Though the findings highlight
10 potential health impacts, the results of case studies will not translate to a larger population.

11 Little information was provided about the population baseline HR-QoL and related facets.
12 Previous research on Services Members entering the military report baseline SF-36 physical and
13 mental health outcomes that are significantly better than those of the general population⁷². This
14 should be addressed in future work. The reports identified were largely based upon male
15 populations and those with amputations. Though the military is predominately male, women are
16 becoming a larger cohort treated within the Veterans Affairs Healthcare System⁷¹. The issues
17 affecting women and personnel with other types of injuries may be different⁷¹. Furthermore, as
18 TBI is a defining injury of the OIF/OEF and potentially affects one's ability to ambulate due to
19 coordination issues as seen in Kontos et al 2015³⁷. A future study should investigate the impacts
20 of a combat induced TBI and polytraumatic injury sustained in combat.

21 There are also limitations to the approach taken in this literature review. Foremost, the
22 classification of study outcomes was determined by a team of three investigators. Though trained
23 on health outcomes and classification methodology, the ratings represent subjective assessments

1 by the investigators regarding the outcome domain assignment. Using prior literature and
2 understanding of HRQoL and functioning, reviewers selected articles they deemed appropriate for
3 each domain and subdomain based on their content. A future assessment should examine and
4 evaluate inter-rater reliability and explore the development and experimentation of a standardized
5 protocol on health outcome measures selected for each facet of the WHO model for HR-QoL. As
6 previous research provides psychometric validation of the SF-36 for mobility impairments, future
7 research should examine this classification scheme and how it relates to overall quality of life
8 scores from global assessments of quality of life⁷³.

9

10 **Conclusions**

11 The following review was conducted to identify and categorize health outcomes
12 measurement tools used to determine specific states of HR-QoL in Post 9/11 Combat Veterans
13 recovering from a combat injury using mobility based Assistive Technology. Investigators placed
14 a slew of outcome measures into distinct domains and subdomains to identify variables of interest
15 during the rehabilitation process and determine the effectiveness of a client's intervention. Using
16 these instruments in a distinctive categorical fashion provides future researchers and clinicians
17 with guidance to model and track crucial domains and subdomains that determine the success of a
18 client's adaptation to a specific health state, in addition to the quality of their care delivery. This
19 can be used to determine policy and decision making among healthcare professionals, people of
20 industry, and clientele when determining the most effective healthcare treatments and
21 interventions. Further research should include these health outcomes as guidance to determine the
22 usability and effectiveness of health-based interventions on improving facets of a Service
23 Member's HR-QoL.

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- 17 Supplemental Table 1. WHO Health Related Quality of Life Domains and Subdomains
- 18 Supplemental Table 2. Process of the Literature Review
- 19 Supplemental Table 3. Extracted Study Data Included in the Review
- 20 Supplemental Table 4. Physical Health Related Outcomes
- 21 Supplemental Table 5. Psychological Well-Being Outcomes
- 22 Supplemental Table 6. Independence Outcomes
- 23 Supplemental Table 7. Social Relations Outcomes
- 24 Supplemental Table 8. Environment Outcomes
- 25 Supplemental Table 9. Religious/Personal/Spiritual Beliefs Outcomes
- 26 Appendix A. Keywords Used for Literature Review